

Explain different Search strategies.

Boolean Searching

This is a very common search technique that integrates search terms based on Boolean logic. There are three types of Boolean searches: AND search, OR search and NOT search.

Boolean AND search enables users to combine two or more search terms through the application of the Boolean AND operator. This type of search will retrieve all items in which every one of the constituent terms appears.

Boolean OR search enables users to combine two or more search terms, thereby allowing the system to retrieve all items that encompass either one or all of the constituent terms.

Boolean NOT search enables users to identify specific terms or keywords that they wish to exclude from the retrieved records.

Proximity Searching

This search facility allows the user to specify whether two search terms should occur adjacent to each other, whether one or two words occur in between the search terms, whether the search terms should occur in the same paragraph irrespective of the intervening words, and so on. (Chowdhury,2004)

For example, if we did a regular phrase search for “classification theories”, we would not retrieve documents mentioning theories of classification, theories involving classification, theories about classification or other similar phrases. But if we do a proximity search, and look for the term classification appearing within a number of certain words (or less) of the term theories, we would be able to retrieve many phrases with those words.

Typically, the proximity operators consist of a letter (either N or W) or word (NEAR) along with a number (which specifies the quantity of words that appear between search terms).

Range Searching

Range searching proves to be particularly beneficial when dealing with numerical information. It is important in selecting records within specific data ranges. The subsequent options are commonly available for range searching:

- Greater than (>)

- Less than (<)
- Equal to (=)
- Not equal to (/=)
- Greater than equal to (>=)
- Less than equal to (<=)

Limiting Searching

The database (which functions within a text retrieval system) encompasses numerous fields that contain unique items of information. The user should be able to refine their search to one or multiple specific fields while formulating their query; text retrieval software generally provides this capability. This process is frequently referred to as field searching: where the user can stipulate that the search terms must be evaluated in one or several fields. However, the efficacy of this method can vary; not all databases manage field specifications in the same way, because of differing structural designs.

Truncation

Truncation search involves conducting a search for various forms of a word that share the same common root. This method is one of the most widely adopted approaches in information retrieval systems. In this technique, the root word is utilized with a truncation mark (*), thus, the search is performed effectively. However, the effectiveness of this method can vary, because not all systems support truncation equally.

For example, if we search the truncated term music, it will retrieve items on

String Searching

String searching is the ability to search on character strings within the body of the text in a record, which is usually available for those fields whose text has not been included in an inverted file, and is, therefore, not pre-indexed. (Chowdhury,2004).

In other words, string searching enables individuals to explore those terms that have yet to be indexed. But, the procedure of string searching aligns the search term character by character with the stored records, so, the search process is exceedingly slow.

Phrase Searching

Phrase searching represents a search technique specifically crafted to restrict search results to those records where the desired phrase appears. However, it is important to note that the effectiveness of this method may vary depending on

the database being used. Although it can significantly refine results, it might also exclude relevant information (because it focuses solely on exact matches). This approach, therefore, serves both advantages and disadvantages.

Phrase searching instructs the database to concentrate exclusively on fetching records in which your terms emerge together as a phrase this excludes all individual instances of the separate words. However, this method is effective because it narrows down the search results significantly. Although it may seem limiting at first, it can actually enhance the relevance of the retrieved information.

This process involves placing a phrase or terms within quotation marks.

For example, if someone want to search a phrase like information retrieval, we have to search as “information retrieval”.

REFERENCES

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